

Open-Source Software Tools for the Implementation of Cyber-Physical Energy Systems (CPEs) over Distributed Research Infrastructures (RIs)

To simplify the implementation of CPES scenarios over distributed RIs, the ERIGRID2 project has developed a set of software tools, with which the available hardware and software can be shared in a co-simulation scheme. These tools provide the following advantages:

- Support for multiple protocols and transports,
- Interoperability through the universal API (uAPI),
- Flexible implementation and re-configuration of CPES co-simulation scenarios,
- Developed under the concept of open-source software.

VILLASframework

VILLAS framework is a toolset for local and geographically distributed real-time co-simulation. The framework consists of several independent components, which can be combined according to requirements and needed functions.

Central is VILLASnode as an interface for the coupling between the involved components. It enables real-time data exchange via various protocols and data formats. VILLASweb provides a web-based user interface with which scenarios, user groups, laboratory infrastructure and measurement results can be managed. The configuration, inventory and control of the involved laboratory infrastructure is realized via

the VILLAScontroller, which exchanges the status as well as control commands and configurations between the virtual control room and the laboratory infrastructure.

Figure 1: The VILLASframework architecture

JANDER

JaNDER is an open-source middleware whose main functionality is the replication of infrastructure data through a cloud node. When data is recorded in a local database, it is mirrored in the cloud database and vice versa. At this level, the data is simply transported without any interpretation of its structure.

Built on top of the replication software, a layer defining the data model for the exchanged measurements can be constructed. This layer makes the data model accessible to the user and maps the model class instances to the appropriate database data structures that need to be replicated. The architecture is depicted in Figure 2.

The building blocks of JaNDER are "cloud node", "RI database", "replication software", and "universal API middleware". The implementation of the APIs enables the use of channels, samples, and events. The API enables JaNDER to operate in various infrastructures, with compatibility and interaction with different transport services.

Figure 2: JaNDER transport equipped with universal API. Each RI is equipped with a local database.

LABLINK

Lablink is an open-source middleware responsible for the management of and real-time data transfer between geographically distributed clients. Lablink provides various clients that have been specifically developed to access hardware (e.g., laboratory equipment) and software (e.g., simulation tools) typically encountered in hardware-in-the-loop testbeds.

Clients rely on functionality provided by the core library (data-driven event handling, connection to transport layer, etc.) to implement their own bindings to hardware or software targets. In its current implementation, Lablink relies on MQTT for messaging between clients over standard TCP/IP connections. Lablink also provides various auxiliary tools, e.g., for logging and visualizing data or for synchronizing the execution of clients.

Figure 3: Lablink architecture concept

Further Info and Documentation

More information via the following QR code:

ERIGrid 2.0 project partners

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